

TEACHING GRAMMAR THROUGH GAMES.

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Abstract: *It is clear that the term “grammar” has meant various things at various times and sometimes several things at one time. This plurality of meaning is characteristic of the present time and is the source of confusions in the discussion of grammar as part of the education of children. There have been taking place violent disputes on the subject of teaching grammar at school. The aim of this term paper is to investigate the steps and stages of teaching grammar in accord with definite rules. The ability to talk about the grammar of a language, to recite its rules, is also very different from ability to speak and understand a language or to read and write it.*

Annotatsiya: *"Grammatika" atamasi har xil vaqtda, ba'zan esa bir nechta narsalarni bir vaqtning o'zida anglatganligi aniq. Bu ma'no ko'pligi bugungi kunga xos bo'lib, bolalarni tarbiyalashning bir qismi sifatida grammatikani muhokama qilishda chalkashlik manbai hisoblanadi. Maktabda grammatikani o'rgatish mavzusida zo'ravonliklar bo'lib o'tmoqda. Ushbu davriy nashrning maqsadi grammatikani aniq qoidalar asosida o'qitish bosqichlari va bosqichlarini o'rganishdir. Tilning grammatikasi haqida gapirish, uning qoidalarini o'qitish qobiliyati, shuningdek, tilni gapirish va tushunish yoki o'qish va yozish qobiliyatidan juda farq qiladi.*

Аннотация: *Понятно, что термин «грамматика» означает разные вещи в разное время, а иногда и несколько вещей одновременно. Множественность значений типична для сегодняшнего дня и является источником путаницы при обсуждении грамматики как части воспитания. Идут горячие дискуссии в отношении преподавать или нет грамматику в школе. Целью этой статьи является изучение этапов и фаз обучения грамматике на основе четких правил. Говорить о грамматике языка очень отличается от умения преподавать его правила, а также от умения говорить и понимать язык или читать и писать.*

Key words: *understand, language, practical skills, commonly-spoken language, important, to think, grammar, vocabulary*

Kalit so'zlar: *tushunish, til, amaliy ko'nikmalar, og'zaki nutq, muhim, o'ylash, grammatika, lug'at.*

Ключевые слова: *понимать, язык, практические навыки, разговорный язык, важно, думать, грамматика, словарный запас.*

INTRODUCTION

Grammar organizes the vocabulary and as a result we have sense units. There is a system of stereotypes, which organizes words into sentences. But what skill does grammar develop? First of all it gives the ability to make up sentences correctly, to reproduce the text adequately. (The development of practical skills and habits). The knowledge of the specific grammar structure helps pupils point out the differences between the mother tongue and the target language. The knowledge of grammar develops abilities to abstract systematize plural facts.

1. WHAT IS THE GRAMMAR?

Grammar is the system of a language. People sometimes describe grammar as the "rules" of a language; but in fact no language has rules*. If we use the word "rules", we suggest that somebody created the rules first and then spoke the language, like a new game. But languages did not start like that. Languages started by people making sounds which evolved into words, phrases and sentences. No commonly-spoken language is fixed. All languages change over time. What we call "grammar" is simply a reflection of a language at a particular time.

Do we need to study grammar to learn a language? The short answer is "no". Very many people in the world speak their own, native language without having studied its grammar. Children start to speak before they even know the word "grammar". But if you are serious about learning a foreign language, the long answer is "yes, grammar can help you to learn a language more quickly and more efficiently." It's important to think of grammar as something that can help you, like a friend. When you understand the grammar (or system) of a language, you can understand many things yourself, without having to ask a teacher or look in a book.

So think of grammar as something good, something positive, something that you can use to find your way - like a signpost or a map.

Grammar is the structural foundation of our ability to express ourselves. The more we are aware of how it works, the more we can monitor the meaning and effectiveness of the way we and others use language. It can help foster precision, detect ambiguity, and exploit the richness of expression available in English. And it

can help everyone--not only teachers of English, but teachers of anything, for all teaching is ultimately a matter of getting to grips with meaning.

It is necessary to know grammar, and it is better to write grammatically than not, but it is well to remember that grammar is common [speech](#) formulated. [Usage](#) is the only test. (William Somerset Maugham, *The Summing Up*, 1938)

To judge by the way some people speak, there is no place for grammar in the language course nowadays; yet it is, in reality, as important as it ever was exercise of correct grammar, if he is to attain any skill of effective use of the language, but he need not know consciously formulated rules to account to him for that he does unconsciously correctly.

In order to understand a language and to express oneself correctly one must assimilate the grammar mechanism of the language studied. Indeed, one may know all the words in a sentence and yet fail to understand it, if one does not see the relation between the words in the given sentence. And vice versa, a sentence may contain one, two, and more unknown words but if one has a good knowledge of the structure of the language one can easily guess the meaning of these words or at least find them in a dictionary.

No speaking is possible without the knowledge of grammar, without the forming of a grammar mechanism.

If learner has acquired such a mechanism, he can produce correct sentences in a foreign language. Paul Roberts writes: "Grammar is something that produces the sentences of a language. By something we mean a speaker of English. If you speak English natively, you have built into you rules of English grammar. In a sense, you are an English grammar. You possess, as an essential part of your being, a very complicated apparatus which enables you to produce infinitely many sentences, all English ones, including many that you have never specifically learned. Furthermore by applying you rule you can easily tell whether a sentence that you hear a grammatical English sentence or not."

A command of English as is envisaged by the school syllabus cannot be ensured without the study of grammar. Pupils need grammar to be able to aud, speak, read, and write in the target language.

Before speaking about the selection of grammar material it is necessary to consider the concept "grammar", i.e., what it meant by "grammar".

By grammar one can mean adequate comprehension and correct usage of words in the act of communication, that is, intuitive knowledge of the grammar of the language. It is a set of reflexes enabling a person to communicate with his associates. Such knowledge is acquired by a child in the mother tongue before he

goes to schools.

This “grammar” functions without the individual’s awareness of technical nomenclature; in other words, he has no idea of the system of the language, and to use all the word-endings for singular and plural, for tense, and all the other grammar rules without special grammar lessons only due to the abundance of auding and speaking. His young mind grasps the facts and “makes simple grammar rules” for arranging the words to express carious thoughts and feelings. This is true because sometimes little children make mistakes by using a common rule for words to which that rule cannot be applied. For example, a little English child might be heard to say “Two mans comed” instead of “Two men come”, because the child is using the plural “s” rule for man to which the rule does not apply, and the past tense ed rule for come which does not obey the ordinary rule for the past tense formation. A little Russian child can say ножов instead of ножей using the case-ending “ов” for ножи to which it does not apply. Such mistakes are corrected as the child grows older and learns more of his language.

By “grammar” we also mean the system of the language, the discovery and description of the nature of language itself. It is not a natural grammar, but a constructed one. There are several constructed grammars: traditional, structural, and transformational grammars. Traditional grammar studies the forms of words (morphology) and how they are put together in sentences (syntax); structural grammar studies structures of various levels of the language (morpheme level) and syntactic level; transformational grammar studies basic structures and transformation rules.

What we need is simplest and shortest grammar that meets the requirements of the school syllabus in foreign languages. This grammar must be simple enough to be grasped and held by any pupil. We cannot say that this problem has been solved.

Since graduates are expected to acquire language proficiency in aural comprehension, speaking and reading grammar material should be selected for the purpose. There exist principles of selecting grammar material both for teaching speaking knowledge (active minimum) and for teaching reading knowledge (passive minimum), the main one is the principle of frequency, i.e., how frequently this or that grammar item occurs. For example, the Present Simple (Indefinite) is frequently used both in conversation and in various texts. Therefore it should be included in the grammar minimum.

For selecting grammar material for reading the principle of polysemia, for instance, is of great importance. Pupils should be taught to distinguish such

grammar items which serve to express different meanings.

The selection of grammar material involves choosing the appropriate kind of linguistic description, i.e., the grammar which constitutes the best base for developing speech habits. Thus the school syllabus reflect a traditional approach to determining grammar material for foreign language teaching, pupils are given sentences patterns or structures, and through these structures they assimilate the English language, acquire grammar mechanisms of speech

The content of grammar teaching is disputable among teachers and methodologists, and there are various approaches to the problem, pupils should, whatever the content of the course, assimilate the ways of fitting words together to form sentences and be able to easily recognize grammar forms and structures while hearing and reading, to reproduce phrases and sentences stored up in their memory and say or write sentences of their own, using grammar items appropriate to the situation.

The grammatical systems of Uzbek and English are fundamentally different. English is an analytical language, in which grammatical meaning is largely expressed through the use of additional words and by changes in word order. Russian is a synthetic language, in which the majority of grammatical forms are created through changes in the structure of words, by means of a developed system of prefixes, suffixes and ending. (p. 121, Brown C. and Jule "Teaching the spoken language", Cambridge, 1983)

No one knows exactly how people learn languages although a great deal of research has been done into the subject.

Many methods have been proposed for the teaching of foreign language. And they have met with varying degrees of success and failure.

We should know that the method by which children are taught must have some effect on their motivation. If they find it deadly boring they will probably become de-motivated, whereas if they have confidence in the method they will find it motivating. Child learners differ from adult learners in many ways. Children are curious, their attention is of a shorter duration, they are quite differently motivated in, and their interests are less specialized. They need frequent of activity; they need activities which are exciting and stimulating their curiosity; they need to be involved in something active.

CONCLUSION

In order to understand a language and express oneself correctly one must assimilate the grammar mechanism of a language. Indeed, one may know all the words in a sentence and yet fail to understand it, if one does not see the

relationship between the words in the given sentence. And vice versa, a sentence may contain one, two, and more unknown words but if one has a good knowledge of the structure of the language one can easily guess the meanings of these words or at least find them in a dictionary, No speaking is possible without the knowledge of grammar, without the forming of a grammar mechanism. Children need grammar to be able to speak, and write in the target language.

Our aim is to form grammar skills and prevent children from making grammar mistakes in their speech. The aim of foreign languages in primary schools is to develop pupils' skills in order to understand speech and participate in conversation.

The method and techniques the teacher should use in teaching children of primary school is the direct method and various techniques which can develop pupils' listening comprehension and speaking.

We have examined two kinds of grammar skills: the reproductive and receptive grammar skills. The reproductive grammar skills give pupils an opportunity to make up their own sentences in oral and written forms in other words to communicate and the receptive grammar skills give them an opportunity to read text and understand it.

To master the reproductive grammar skills one should study the basic sentences or models (grammar is presented as itself in the basic sentences), to master the receptive grammar skills one should identify and analyze the grammar item. We teach children to read by means of grammar. It reveals the relationship between the words in the given sentence.

We have such a conclusion that the forming of grammar skills depends on training. Training is of great importance to realize the grammar item. We must use a lot of training exercises for the assimilation of grammar. We should provide the motivation of learn English, encourage children to communicate and remember that the correction of errors in the early stages of a language course may foster the following negative aspects:

- children lose confidence when they have fear of making grammar mistakes
- children become reluctant to take risks: they only the say the information they know they can say

We should realize the importance of training exercises and the role of the individual approach to teaching the children. Besides, the teacher must have a clear idea of the grammar of the language, its structure and usage; everything he teaches must be based on it; he should always be conscious of introducing or practicing some point of grammar.

REFERENCES:

1. Rogova, G.V., "Methods of teaching English"; M.,1970
2. Harmer, Jeremy, "the practice English language teaching"; London-New York; Longman,1991
3. Синявская, Е.В. и др., «Вопросы методики обучения иностранным языком за рубежом.» /сост.: Е.В.Синявская, М.М. Васильева, С.В.Калинина/; М., Просвещение,1978
4. Handschin, Charles H., "Methods of teaching modern languages."; N.Y.,World Book Co.,1926
5. Bennett, William Arthur., "Aspects of Language and language teaching."; London-New York., Cambridge univ. press, 1968
6. Lado Robert and Fries Charles C., "English pattern practices. Establishing the patterns as habits."; The univ. of Michigan press, 1970
7. F.L Billows., "The Techniques of Language Teaching."; Longman, 1962
8. Fries, Charles Carpenter., "Teaching and Learning English as a foreign language."; The univ. of Michigan press, 1964
9. Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rogers., " Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching."; Cambridge univ. press, 1986
10. Elaine Tarone and George Yule., "Focus on Language Learner."; Oxford univ., 1991
11. Michael H. Long, Jack C. Richards., "Methology in Tesol: A book of Readings."; USA., 1987
12. Pooley, Robert., "teaching English grammar."; N.Y., Appleton – Century – Crofts, 1957

